

The Role of the Cooperating Teacher in the Pre-Service Teacher Journey

Dr. Traci Johnson & Dr. Tami Shelley

Auburn University at Montgomery, Montgomery, AL 36117

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*Corresponding Author: Dr. Traci Johnson

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Pre-service teacher preparation during internship is important and complex. Moreover, these are crucial relationships and roles represented during this educational journey. The cooperating teachers play a vital role and are typically eager and willing to collaborate with pre-service teachers. However, cooperating teachers, despite being experienced in pedagogy and teaching children, frequently need additional training in andragogy, adult education, and guidance concerning the significant role they fulfill during the internship process. As a result of the relationship, this paper highlights the need for better preparation of mentor teachers to support beginning educators effectively.

Keywords: Pre-Service Teachers, Teacher Preparation, Internship, Cooperating Teachers, Teacher Training, Pedagogy, Mentorship.

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Pre-service teacher preparation during internship is important and complex. There are important relationships and roles represented and at work during this journey.

The three main parts of the team during internship are the preservice teacher/intern (or teacher candidate), the cooperating teacher, and the university supervisor. The preservice teacher/intern (or teacher candidate) is an individual enrolled in practitioner preparation programs leading to teacher licensure. The cooperating teacher is an appropriately state licensed classroom teacher who provides guidance and supervision to teacher candidates in their classroom during the candidates' field experience (or internship) in a school. The college or university supervisor is a qualified employee or individual contracted by the college or university offering teacher preparation who provide guidance and supervision to teacher candidates during the candidates' clinical experiences in the schools. This team of three is an important part of directing field, clinical, or student teaching/internship experiences for the teacher candidate. This article will focus on the role of the cooperating teacher during the internship phase of this journey.

Cooperating teachers are eager and willing to work with student teachers.

However, they may not be prepared to be in effective mentor

relationships. (Izadinia, 2015)

Cooperating teachers hold a dualistic position of being a mentor and while still being responsible for their classroom. Most cooperating teachers are not trained to mentor and provide quality feedback to student teachers. The cooperating teacher is usually simultaneously responsible for their own classroom and the intern. Research conducted over thirty years ago, points to the internship placement and the role of the cooperating teacher as the two most influential factors in the quality of the internship experience (Norris et al, 2002). The cooperating teacher directly influences the pre-service teacher's self-efficacy during internship. Teacher self-efficacy is defined as a judgment of one's own capabilities to bring about desired outcomes of student engagement and learning, even when students are difficult or unmotivated (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001). Teachers who enter the teaching profession with higher self-efficacy often avoid burnout and remain in the classroom as a professional educator (Swan et al., 2011). Due to the important role of the cooperating teacher, preparation and training for this pivotal mentorship role is critical. It is often thought that if a teacher is a strong practitioner in the classroom, they will be a great mentor as well, but this may not always be true. The skills necessary to be an effective mentor are skills that can be learned and developed over time as they are consistently

demonstrated in teacher preparation programs (Hennisen et al., 2011; Darling-Hammond 2010).

A step in the right direction is laying the foundation for the understanding between the skills of **pedagogy** and the skills of **andragogy**. Pedagogy usually focuses on teaching children using teacher led instruction within a structured environment. Andragogy focuses on adult learners and involves self-directed learning with the goal being experience-based knowledge with practical application. In the pre-service teacher journey up until internship, the intern has been in the student (being teacher instructed) side of the pedagogy equation. In the elementary classroom, the cooperating teacher daily assumes the classroom pedagogical role of the teacher developing and delivering the instruction for elementary students. Interns and cooperating teachers find themselves in totally different roles as they step into internship. Both are now in a classroom together as teacher and mentor, the andragogy model is a better match for their learning and development. The five-andragogy principles according to Knowles (1985) are:

1. *Regarding the concept of the learner:* Adults need to be involved in the planning and evaluation of their instruction. Adults tend to be more self-directed in their own learning.
2. *Regarding the role of the learner's experience:* Experience (including mistakes) provides the basis for learning activities.
3. *Regarding readiness to learn:* Adults are most interested in learning subjects that have immediate relevance to their job or personal life, such as moving, loss of a job, promotion, or divorce.
4. *Regarding orientation to learning:* Adult learning is problem-centered rather than content-oriented (Kearsley, 2010).
5. *Regarding motivation to learn:* It is recognized that adults do respond to external motivation, such as wages, promotions; however, in this model adults respond to internal motivations, such as "self-esteem, recognition, a better quality of life, greater self-confidence, and self-actualization" (Knowles, 1984, p. 12).

This change of roles requires adjustment from the intern and cooperating teacher for internship to be a fully successful experience. The overall goal in internship is for each to learn from the other as they work side by side in the same classroom. Both cooperating teachers and their student teachers can learn from one another to advance their professional knowledge and practice (Aderibige, 2013). Internship for a pre-service teacher and the cooperating teacher can most accurately be described as a "mentorship" relationship. Mentoring is described as "interpersonal relationships that comprise a series of purposeful, social interactions" (Ambrosetti, 2014).

The relationship should be collaborative, where they are in the experience together, instead of a supervisor/supervisee role where there is a power structure in place. The evolution of the mentor/mentee relationship lays the foundation for skills to develop as the intern and cooperating teacher ask questions, make decisions, reflect, and develop their teaching skills.

For the internship experience to be successful, it is evident that both the intern and cooperating teacher need formal guidance and direction in the following areas:

Understanding of Socio-Cultural and Constructivism Theories (Social Context for Learning)

The cooperating teacher guides the student teacher from what they bring from their teacher preparation courses and practicums to actual practice in a classroom, the social setting, where the student teacher gradually can successfully teach unaided. Learning is immersed in the social interaction of the school setting, collaboration, and sharing of skills (Kell, 2020).

Knowledgeable teachers, scaffold in many different types of structures, such as encouragement, suggestions, or the decomposition of skill to allow the growth of the learner (Tracey & Morrow, 2011).

Mentor/Mentee Relationship Theories and Expectations through the Lens of Andragogy

The evolution of the mentor/mentee relationship builds the background for skills to develop. The relationship should be collaborative, where they are in the experience together, instead of a supervisor/supervisee role where there is a power structure in place. Both cooperating teachers and their student teachers can learn from one another to advance their professional knowledge and practice (Aderibige, 2013). In the framework of andragogy, also during this time, the student teacher has moved from being instructed what to learn, to making their own decisions on what they need from their mentor teacher.

Effective Reflective Feedback

According to Stoughton, (2007) reflective practice can be powerful in becoming intentional and self-aware through your actions and perceptions. Through reflection, pre-service teachers are motivated to revisit moments in their teaching through multiple lenses making connections between practices and knowledge. Cooperating teachers give feedback to close the gap between the present performances to better performances (Cornelius & Nagro, 2014).

Modeling/Demonstration of Expert Teaching Practices

Cooperating teachers must be able to be a consistent source of modeling for the student teacher. Every interaction, professional, casual, verbal and non-verbal between the cooperating teacher and their students is scrutinized by the student teacher. Cooperating teachers prepare student teachers of practices such as classroom management, content knowledge, lesson planning, assessment, and parent communication (Kell, 2020).

Many cooperating teachers have little or no training on being a mentor or working with adult learners, and even though there is a strong interest in helping an intern, the outcome is a "hit or miss" experience. The benefits of accepting a role as a cooperating teacher are often positive because of the long-lasting relationships, working toward a common goal, and

exposure to fresh new ideas from their intern (Anderson & Stillman, 2013). However, cooperating teachers, even though experienced in pedagogy and teaching children, often need training and guidance concerning the important role they play during internship.

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